

Partial Relaxation for Near-Field Channel Parameter Estimation: Algorithms and Cramér–Rao Bounds

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Abstract—We consider near-field channel parameter estimation in a multi-user uplink setup where users lie in the radiative near-field of a large-aperture base-station array. Based on the partial relaxation (PR) principle, we estimate the desired user’s range and azimuth under a spherical-wave model while representing the other multi-user contributions via an unstructured nuisance component. We develop two estimators: a PR-based maximum likelihood estimator with known pilots and a PR-based covariance-fitting estimator for unknown symbols. To analyze performance, we derive the corresponding Cramér–Rao bounds for the known pilots and unknown symbols cases. We further benchmark the proposed estimators against a near-field two-dimensional multiple-signal-classification baseline. Numerical results show that the proposed PR estimators yield lower normalized mean-squared error than a near-field two-dimensional subspace baseline and approach their respective Cramér–Rao bounds at moderate-to-high signal-to-noise ratios with sufficiently many snapshots.

Index Terms—Cramér–Rao bounds, maximum likelihood, near-field channel parameter estimation, partial relaxation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Multiple input multiple output (MIMO) has become a cornerstone of contemporary wireless systems, enabling not only substantial gains in spectral efficiency via multi-antenna beamforming and spatial multiplexing, but also a host of beyond-connectivity services (e.g., localization and sensing) [1]–[3]. For most of these applications, acquiring channel state information with low pilot overhead and manageable complexity is crucial [1]. Recent works have noted that, as base station (BS) arrays continue to scale in aperture and number of antenna elements, the accuracy of channel acquisition increasingly depends on estimation strategies that explicitly exploit the underlying propagation structure [4], [5]. In large-aperture deployments, users may operate in the radiative near-field (Fresnel region), where wavefront curvature is non-negligible. In this regime, the phase evolution across

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the array depends jointly on angle and range, rendering conventional far-field (planar-wave) models inaccurate. This motivates the search for near-field parametric estimation methods that remain reliable under practical snapshot and signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) budgets, especially in multi-user uplinks where interference is unavoidable. Subspace-based approaches have been widely used for near-field parameter estimation, most notably two-dimensional MULTiple SIGNAL Classification (2D-MUSIC) adapted to spherical-wave array responses, which jointly estimate angle and range [4]. These approaches provide a principled baseline, but their reliance on a finite-sample covariance estimate makes them sensitive to limited data records and noise, which can lead to subspace leakage and degraded parameter estimates. Moreover, in multi-user uplinks, their performance can deteriorate in the presence of strong interference and closely spaced users.

To better handle multi-user interference, prior work has developed the partial relaxation (PR) principle for array parameter estimation. In PR, the user of interest is kept parametric while the remaining users are absorbed by a relaxed (unstructured) nuisance component, which reduces modeling burden while mitigating interference [6]. Subsequent studies reported that PR-based estimators can outperform subspace-based methods [6]–[8]. However, PR has not yet been developed and analyzed for radiative near-field parametric estimation.

Motivated by this gap, we extend the PR framework to near-field channel parameter estimation under a spherical-wave model. The key idea is to retain a structured near-field model for the desired user, enabling robust estimation of the desired user’s geometric parameters.

Specifically, we develop two estimators: partial-relaxation maximum likelihood (PR-ML) for the known-pilot case and partial-relaxation covariance fitting (PR-CF) for the unknown symbols case via covariance fitting. In addition, we derive the associated PR-type benchmarks: the Partial-Relaxation Cramér–Rao Bound for Known Pilots (PR-CRB_p) for the known-pilot formulation and the Partial-Relaxation Cramér–Rao Bound for Unknown Symbols (PR-CRB_u) for the Unknown Symbols setting, thereby providing performance limits consistent with the adopted partial-relaxation modeling.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the system and near-field signal model. Sec-

tion III introduces the proposed PR-based estimators. Section IV derives the corresponding bounds. Section V provides numerical results, and Section VI concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a multi-user uplink two-dimensional (2D) scenario, where the BS and the users lie on the same plane, in which an N -element uniform linear array (ULA)¹ at the BS receives L snapshots from K users located in the radiative near-field, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

The k -th user in the radiative near-field is parameterized by

$$\boldsymbol{\theta}_k \triangleq (d_k, \phi_k), \quad (1)$$

where d_k is the range from the array reference point to the user, and ϕ_k is the corresponding azimuth angle (measured from the array axis, as in Fig. 1). Let the n -th antenna location be $\bar{x}_n = \delta_n \Delta$, $n = 1, \dots, N$, where $\delta_n = (n - \frac{N+1}{2})$ and Δ is the inter-element spacing, set to half of the wavelength (i.e., $\Delta = \lambda/2$). Under the spherical-wave model, the propagation distance between antenna element n and user k is given by [9]

$$r_{n,k} = \sqrt{d_k^2 + (\delta_n \Delta)^2 - 2d_k \Delta \delta_n \cos(\phi_k)}. \quad (2)$$

Assuming line-of-sight propagation, the channel between antenna element n and user k is represented as

$$h(d_k, \phi_k) = \sqrt{\beta_{n,k}} e^{-j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} r_{n,k}}, \quad (3)$$

where $\beta_{n,k}$ denotes the free-space channel gain between antenna n and user k . Following [10], the gain can be approximated as $\beta_{n,k} \approx \beta_k$, with

$$\beta_k = \frac{\lambda^2 \sin(\phi_k)}{16\pi d_k^2}, \quad \forall n. \quad (4)$$

This approximation is valid when the propagation distance exceeds twice the array aperture, such that amplitude variations across the spherical wavefront can be neglected while the phase variations remain non-negligible [11].

Using (3) and (4), we model the near-field channel vector to user k as

$$\mathbf{h}(d_k, \phi_k) = \sqrt{\beta_k} [e^{-j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} r_{1,k}}, \dots, e^{-j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} r_{N,k}}]^\top. \quad (5)$$

At time instance ℓ , the received snapshot can be written as

$$\mathbf{y}[\ell] = \sqrt{P_s} \mathbf{H} \mathbf{D}_\psi \mathbf{s}[\ell] + \mathbf{w}[\ell], \quad \ell = 1, \dots, L, \quad (6)$$

where P_s denotes the symbol transmit power (which is the pilot power in the known-pilot regime), and where $\mathbf{D}_\psi \triangleq \text{diag}(e^{j\psi_1}, \dots, e^{j\psi_K}) \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times K}$ models the unknown per-user phase offsets. Define

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{H} &\triangleq [\mathbf{h}(d_1, \phi_1) \ \dots \ \mathbf{h}(d_K, \phi_K)] \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times K}, \\ \mathbf{y}[\ell] &\triangleq [y_1[\ell] \ \dots \ y_N[\ell]]^\top \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}, \\ \mathbf{s}[\ell] &\triangleq [s_1[\ell] \ \dots \ s_K[\ell]]^\top \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times 1}, \\ \mathbf{w}[\ell] &\triangleq [w_1[\ell] \ \dots \ w_N[\ell]]^\top \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}, \end{aligned}$$

¹Note that the proposed model is readily extendable to general array geometries.

Fig. 1: The BS employs an N -element ULA. The channel between antenna element n and user k is characterized by the near-field channel vector $\mathbf{h}_k(d_k, \phi_k)$, where d_k is the range from the array reference point to the user location, and ϕ_k is the azimuth angle measured with respect to the array axis. Users are assumed to lie in the radiative near-field region, i.e., between $2D$ and R_F , where $D = (N - 1)\lambda/2$ and $R_F = 2D^2/\lambda$.

where \mathbf{H} is the multi-user near-field channel matrix, $\mathbf{y}[\ell]$ contains the received samples, and $\mathbf{s}[\ell]$ stacks the transmitted pilot symbols of the K users. The noise $\mathbf{w}[\ell]$ is additive, where each entry follows an independent complex Gaussian distribution with zero mean and variance σ^2 . The received data collected over L snapshots are arranged into the matrix

$$\mathbf{Y} = [\mathbf{y}[1] \ \dots \ \mathbf{y}[L]] \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times L}. \quad (7)$$

III. CHANNEL ESTIMATION VIA PARTIAL RELAXATION

This section presents two PR-based estimators for near-field parameter estimation. We first develop PR-ML for the case of known pilots and then present PR-CF for the case of unknown symbols. In both formulations, the key idea is to preserve a parametric near-field model for the desired user while representing the remaining multi-user interference by a relaxed (unstructured) nuisance component.

a) PR-ML with known pilots: The pilot sequences of all K users are assumed known at the BS. We consider user 1 as the desired user whose value of $\boldsymbol{\theta}_1$ is to be estimated. The received data matrix can be modeled as

$$\mathbf{Y} = \underbrace{\alpha \mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1) \mathbf{s}_1^\top}_{\text{desired user}} + \underbrace{\mathbf{B} \mathbf{S}_B^\top}_{\text{relaxed (all other users)}} + \mathbf{W}, \quad (8)$$

The scalar parameter $\alpha = \sqrt{P_s} e^{j\psi_1} \in \mathbb{C}$ has to be estimated along with $\boldsymbol{\theta}_1$ and denotes the unknown complex gain of the desired component. Furthermore, $\mathbf{s}_1 \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times 1}$ denotes the known pilot sequence of the desired user, and the (known) pilot sequences of the remaining users are stacked in

$$\mathbf{S}_B \triangleq [\mathbf{s}_2 \ \mathbf{s}_3 \ \dots \ \mathbf{s}_K] \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times (K-1)}. \quad (9)$$

Here, $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times (K-1)}$ is a relaxed version of the spatial signatures (channels) of the non-desired users, i.e., it is not constrained by a geometric near-field parameterization, and it implicitly absorbs the transmit-power scaling $\sqrt{P_s}$ and the phase offsets of the interfering users (i.e., the corresponding

diagonal entries of \mathbf{D}_ψ). Accordingly, $\mathbf{B}\mathbf{S}_B^\top$ provides a relaxed representation of the aggregate contribution of all other users, and $\mathbf{W} \triangleq [\mathbf{w}[1] \ \cdots \ \mathbf{w}[L]] \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times L}$ collects the noise snapshots,

Under white Gaussian noise, the log-likelihood is equivalent to the least-squares cost

$$J(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1, \alpha, \mathbf{B}) = \|\mathbf{Y} - \alpha \mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1) \mathbf{s}_1^\top - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{S}_B^\top\|_F^2. \quad (10)$$

To obtain a concentrated criterion in $(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1, \alpha)$, we first eliminate the relaxed nuisance matrix \mathbf{B} in closed form. For fixed $(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1, \alpha)$, define the residual

$$\mathbf{R}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1, \alpha) \triangleq \mathbf{Y} - \alpha \mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1) \mathbf{s}_1^\top, \quad (11)$$

so that $J(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1, \alpha, \mathbf{B}) = \|\mathbf{R}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1, \alpha) - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{S}_B^\top\|_F^2$. For fixed $(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1, \alpha)$, the LS minimizer over \mathbf{B} is

$$\mathbf{B}^*(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1, \alpha) = \mathbf{R}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1, \alpha) \mathbf{S}_B (\mathbf{S}_B^\text{H} \mathbf{S}_B)^{-1}. \quad (12)$$

Substituting (12) into (10) yields the concentrated cost

$$J(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1, \alpha) = \|\mathbf{R}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1, \alpha) \mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{S}_B}^\perp\|_F^2, \quad (13)$$

where the orthogonal projector onto the complement of $\text{span}(\mathbf{S}_B)$ is

$$\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{S}_B}^\perp = \mathbf{I}_L - \mathbf{S}_B (\mathbf{S}_B^\text{H} \mathbf{S}_B)^{-1} \mathbf{S}_B^\text{H}, \quad (14)$$

Assumption: \mathbf{S}_B has full column rank with $L \geq K - 1$. Next, eliminate α . Define

$$\tilde{\mathbf{Y}} \triangleq \mathbf{Y} \mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{S}_B}^\perp, \quad \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_1^\top \triangleq \mathbf{s}_1^\top \mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{S}_B}^\perp \quad (\text{so that } \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_1 \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times 1}), \quad (15)$$

so that $J(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1, \alpha) = \|\tilde{\mathbf{Y}} - \alpha \mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1) \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_1^\top\|_F^2$. Minimizing over α gives

$$\alpha^*(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1) = \frac{\mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1)^\text{H} \tilde{\mathbf{Y}} \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_1}{\|\mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1)\|_2^2 \|\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_1\|_2^2}. \quad (16)$$

Substituting (16) into (13) yields an equivalent maximization of the PR-ML score

$$S_{\text{PR-ML}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1) = \frac{|\mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1)^\text{H} \tilde{\mathbf{Y}} \mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{S}_B}^\perp \mathbf{s}_1^\top|^2}{\|\mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1)\|_2^2 \|\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{S}_B}^\perp \mathbf{s}_1^\top\|_2^2}. \quad (17)$$

The score in (17) corresponds to a matched-filter criterion after projecting the interference subspace spanned by \mathbf{S}_B . Finally, the desired user parameters are obtained via a 2-D search:

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_1 = \arg \max S_{\text{PR-ML}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1). \quad (18)$$

b) PR-CF with unknown symbols: In the unknown symbols case, we adopt the PR-CF framework of [8]. The main adaptation in this work is to replace the far-field channel response in [8] with the proposed *near-field* spherical-wave channel vector in (5). Accordingly, for a generic desired user k , we evaluate the PR-CF criterion over (d_k, ϕ_k) using $\mathbf{h}(d_k, \phi_k)$.

The sample covariance matrix [8]

$$\mathbf{R}_b \triangleq \mathbf{Y}\mathbf{Y}^\text{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}. \quad (19)$$

Following [8], the PR-CF spectrum is computed as

$$f_{\text{CF}}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=K}^N \lambda_i^2 \left(\mathbf{R}_b - \frac{\mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_k) \mathbf{h}^\text{H}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_k)}{\mathbf{h}^\text{H}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_k) \mathbf{R}_b^{-1} \mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_k)} \right)}, \quad (20)$$

where $\lambda_i(\cdot)$ denotes the i -th largest eigenvalue of its matrix argument. The estimates of $\boldsymbol{\theta}_k$ are obtained as the location of K largest maxima of the objective function in (20).

IV. CRAMÉR–RAO BOUNDS FOR PARTIAL RELAXATION

In this section, we derive the Cramér–Rao bounds (CRBs) associated with the proposed PR framework for radiative near-field parameter estimation. Specifically, we consider two cases: (i) the PR-CRB_p for PR-ML with known pilots, and (ii) the PR-CRB_u for PR-CF with Unknown Symbols.

a) PR-CRB_p for known pilots: In the PR framework, the unknown parameter vector is partitioned into a *structured* component associated with the desired user and an *unstructured* component that captures the relaxed interference block. This partitioning enables deriving a partial-relaxation bound for the desired parameters after eliminating the nuisance block, a bound for the relaxed block itself, as well as the joint bound for the complete parameter set.

We consider the PR data model in (8). Using the identity $\text{vec}(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{X}\mathbf{O}) = (\mathbf{O}^\top \otimes \mathbf{A}) \text{vec}(\mathbf{X})$, we obtain

$$\mathbf{y} = (\mathbf{s}_1 \otimes \mathbf{I}_N) \alpha \mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1) + (\mathbf{S}_B \otimes \mathbf{I}_N) \mathbf{b} + \mathbf{w}, \quad (21)$$

where $\mathbf{b} \triangleq \text{vec}(\mathbf{B})$, and \mathbf{s}_1 and \mathbf{S}_B are assumed known in this subsection. The noise satisfies

$$\mathbf{w} \triangleq \text{vec}(\mathbf{W}), \quad \mathbf{w} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}_{NL}). \quad (22)$$

Hence, the conditional mean of the data matrix is

$$\mathbf{M}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) = \alpha \mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1) \mathbf{s}_1^\top + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{S}_B^\top. \quad (23)$$

Vectorizing, the conditional mean of $\mathbf{y} = \text{vec}(\mathbf{Y})$ is

$$\mathbf{m}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) = (\mathbf{s}_1 \otimes \mathbf{I}_N) \alpha \mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1) + (\mathbf{S}_B \otimes \mathbf{I}_N) \mathbf{b}. \quad (24)$$

We form a real-valued parameter vector by stacking real and imaginary parts as

$$\boldsymbol{\eta} = \underbrace{[d_1, \phi_1, \Re\{\alpha\}, \Im\{\alpha\}]^\top}_{\triangleq \boldsymbol{\vartheta}^\top} \underbrace{[\Re\{\mathbf{b}\}^\top, \Im\{\mathbf{b}\}^\top]^\top}_{\triangleq \boldsymbol{\xi}^\top}. \quad (25)$$

PR-CRB_p for the structured desired parameters: For a deterministic complex Gaussian model with white noise, the Fisher information matrix (FIM) follows the Bangs formula [12]

$$\mathbf{F}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) = \frac{2}{\sigma^2} \Re \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{m}(\boldsymbol{\eta})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\eta}} \right)^\text{H} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{m}(\boldsymbol{\eta})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\eta}} \right) \right\}. \quad (26)$$

Partition the FIM according to $\boldsymbol{\eta} = [\boldsymbol{\vartheta}^\top, \boldsymbol{\xi}^\top]^\top$ as

$$\mathbf{F}(\boldsymbol{\eta}) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{J}_{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}\boldsymbol{\vartheta}} & \mathbf{J}_{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}\boldsymbol{\xi}} \\ \mathbf{J}_{\boldsymbol{\xi}\boldsymbol{\vartheta}} & \mathbf{J}_{\boldsymbol{\xi}\boldsymbol{\xi}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \boldsymbol{\vartheta} \triangleq [d_1, \phi_1, \Re\{\alpha\}, \Im\{\alpha\}]^\top. \quad (27)$$

Eliminating the relaxed nuisance parameters $\boldsymbol{\xi}$ via the Schur complement yields the effective Fisher information

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{eff}} \triangleq \mathbf{J}_{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}\boldsymbol{\vartheta}} - \mathbf{J}_{\boldsymbol{\vartheta}\boldsymbol{\xi}} \mathbf{J}_{\boldsymbol{\xi}\boldsymbol{\xi}}^{-1} \mathbf{J}_{\boldsymbol{\xi}\boldsymbol{\vartheta}}, \quad (28)$$

and the partial-relaxation bound for the structured parameters is

$$\mathbf{PR-CRB}(\boldsymbol{\vartheta}) = \mathbf{F}_{\text{eff}}^{-1}. \quad (29)$$

The top-left 2×2 principal sub-matrix of (29) provides the bound for (d_1, ϕ_1) .

Required Jacobian terms: From (24), the required Jacobian blocks are: Let $\mathbf{h}_1 \triangleq \mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1)$, $\mathbf{h}_{d_1} \triangleq \partial \mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1)/\partial d_1$, and $\mathbf{h}_{\phi_1} \triangleq \partial \mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1)/\partial \phi_1$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}(\boldsymbol{\eta})}{\partial \Re\{\alpha\}} &= (\mathbf{s}_1 \otimes \mathbf{I}_N) \mathbf{h}_1, & \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}(\boldsymbol{\eta})}{\partial \Im\{\alpha\}} &= j(\mathbf{s}_1 \otimes \mathbf{I}_N) \mathbf{h}_1, \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}(\boldsymbol{\eta})}{\partial \Re\{\mathbf{b}\}} &= (\mathbf{S}_B \otimes \mathbf{I}_N), & \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}(\boldsymbol{\eta})}{\partial \Im\{\mathbf{b}\}} &= j(\mathbf{S}_B \otimes \mathbf{I}_N), \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}(\boldsymbol{\eta})}{\partial d_1} &= (\mathbf{s}_1 \otimes \mathbf{I}_N) \alpha \mathbf{h}_{d_1}, & \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}(\boldsymbol{\eta})}{\partial \phi_1} &= (\mathbf{s}_1 \otimes \mathbf{I}_N) \alpha \mathbf{h}_{\phi_1}. \end{aligned}$$

The near-field derivatives $\partial \mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1)/\partial d_1$ and $\partial \mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1)/\partial \phi_1$ follow from the spherical-wave model; we adopt the expressions reported in [4].

Unstructured bound for the relaxed block: The Fisher information sub-matrix associated with the nuisance parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\xi}$ is

$$\mathbf{J}_{\boldsymbol{\xi}\boldsymbol{\xi}} = \frac{2P_s}{\sigma^2} \Re\{(\mathbf{S}_B^H \mathbf{S}_B) \otimes \mathbf{I}_N\}. \quad (30)$$

Hence, the corresponding unstructured bound is obtained as

$$\text{CRB}_{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^{\text{unstr}} = \mathbf{J}_{\boldsymbol{\xi}\boldsymbol{\xi}}^{-1} = \frac{\sigma^2}{2P_s} (\Re\{(\mathbf{S}_B^H \mathbf{S}_B) \otimes \mathbf{I}_N\})^{-1}. \quad (31)$$

Joint CRB: The joint CRB for the complete real-valued parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\eta} = [\boldsymbol{\vartheta}^T, \boldsymbol{\xi}^T]^T$ is obtained as the inverse of the full Fisher information matrix (FIM) in (27), i.e., the joint CRB is given by $\mathbf{F}(\boldsymbol{\eta})^{-1}$. This joint bound captures the coupling between the structured parameters $\boldsymbol{\vartheta}$ and the relaxed nuisance block $\boldsymbol{\xi}$ under the PR model, and the corresponding $\boldsymbol{\vartheta}$ -block is equal to the partial-relaxation bound in (29) via Schur-complement elimination of $\boldsymbol{\xi}$.

To obtain the joint CRB on the channel, we map the joint parameter bound to the channel domain via the Jacobian. Let $\mathbf{c} \triangleq \alpha \mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1)$ denote the desired-user channel. Then,

$$\text{CRB}_{\mathbf{h}} = \mathbf{J}_c \mathbf{F}(\boldsymbol{\eta})^{-1} \mathbf{J}_c^H, \quad (32)$$

where $\mathbf{J}_c \triangleq \partial \mathbf{c} / \partial \boldsymbol{\vartheta}^T$.

b) PR-CRB_u for unknown symbols: We derive the PR-CRB_u as a performance benchmark for near-field parameter estimation under *unknown symbols*. In this setting, a constrained formulation is required to obtain a finite bound. Consider the PR data model in (8), but now with unknown symbol sequences. If the relaxed term is written as a bilinear product $\mathbf{B}\mathbf{S}^H$ with both factors treated as unknown, then for any invertible matrix $\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{C}^{K-1 \times K-1}$,

$$\mathbf{B}\mathbf{S}^H = (\mathbf{B}\mathbf{Q})(\mathbf{S}\mathbf{Q}^{-1})^H, \quad (33)$$

which shows that the factorization is not identifiable since infinitely many pairs generate the same product. Consequently, the Fisher information matrix becomes singular and the standard (unconstrained) CRB does not exist; see, e.g., [13]. To resolve this ambiguity, we represent the relaxed block using a fixed-rank factorization (rank-one below) and impose standard identifying constraints, which leads to a constrained bound (constrained CRB) [14].

Fixed-rank relaxed model: To obtain a finite bound under unknown symbols, we represent the relaxed nuisance term by a fixed-rank factorization of rank r . In this work, we set $r = K - 1$ to match the number of interfering users aggregated in the relaxed block. For clarity, we first present the rank-one case ($r = 1$) and then state the extension to $r = K - 1$.

Rank-one relaxed model: We start with the minimal nontrivial choice, namely $r = 1$, and represent the relaxed term as

$$\mathbf{B}\mathbf{S}^H \triangleq \gamma \mathbf{u}\mathbf{v}^H, \quad \gamma \in \mathbb{R}_+, \quad \mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}, \quad \mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times 1}. \quad (34)$$

Substituting (34) into the PR data model yields

$$\mathbf{Y} = \alpha \mathbf{h}(d_1, \phi_1) \mathbf{s}_1^T + \gamma \mathbf{u}\mathbf{v}^H + \mathbf{W}, \quad (35)$$

where $\mathbf{s}_1 \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times 1}$ is unknown.

Interpretation: The factor $\gamma \mathbf{u}\mathbf{v}^H$ provides a parsimonious representation of the aggregate interference, where \mathbf{u} captures the (unstructured) spatial signature across the N antennas, \mathbf{v} captures the temporal signature across the L snapshots, and γ is a nonnegative scaling coefficient that absorbs the interference power within the relaxed block.

Identifying constraints: Although the rank-one relaxation removes the general \mathbf{Q} -rotation ambiguity of bilinear factorizations, the decomposition $\gamma \mathbf{u}\mathbf{v}^H$ remains invariant to a nonzero complex rescaling, i.e.,

$$(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) \mapsto (c\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}/c^*), \quad c \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\}. \quad (36)$$

Moreover, when the desired symbol sequence \mathbf{s}_1 is unknown, the pair (α, \mathbf{s}_1) is identifiable only up to a common complex scale/phase factor. To enforce identifiability (and thus obtain a finite constrained CRB), we impose the following constraints:

$$\|\mathbf{u}\|_2^2 = 1, \quad (37)$$

$$\|\mathbf{v}\|_2^2 = 1, \quad (38)$$

$$\Im\{\mathbf{u}\}_1 = 0, \quad (39)$$

$$\Re\{\mathbf{s}_1\}_1 = 1, \quad \Im\{\mathbf{s}_1\}_1 = 0. \quad (40)$$

The unit-norm constraints in (37)–(38) fix the scaling of the spatial and temporal signatures so that γ captures the power of the relaxed interference component, while (39) resolves the remaining global phase ambiguity of the rank-one factorization by forcing the first entry of \mathbf{u} to be real. Finally, (40) removes the two real degrees of freedom (overall amplitude and global phase) that are otherwise indistinguishable between α and \mathbf{s}_1 . Under these constraints, the parametrization is identifiable and supports the constrained CRB construction [14].

Data mean and vectorization: Let $\boldsymbol{\zeta}$ collect the unknown parameters in the rank-one model (35), and define the mean of \mathbf{Y} as

$$\mathbf{M}(\boldsymbol{\zeta}) \triangleq \alpha \mathbf{h}(d_1, \phi_1) \mathbf{s}_1^T + \gamma \mathbf{u}\mathbf{v}^H \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times L}. \quad (41)$$

We further define the vectorized mean

$$\mathbf{m}(\boldsymbol{\zeta}) \triangleq \text{vec}(\mathbf{M}(\boldsymbol{\zeta})) \in \mathbb{C}^{NL \times 1}. \quad (42)$$

Note that $\text{vec}(\mathbf{u}\mathbf{v}^H) = \mathbf{v}^* \otimes \mathbf{u}$.

Fisher information matrix (unconstrained): We form a real-valued parameter vector by stacking real and imaginary parts as

$$\zeta \triangleq [d_1, \phi_1, \Re\{\alpha\}, \Im\{\alpha\}, \Re\{\mathbf{s}_1\}^\top, \Im\{\mathbf{s}_1\}^\top, \gamma, \Re\{\mathbf{u}\}^\top, \Im\{\mathbf{u}\}^\top, \Re\{\mathbf{v}\}^\top, \Im\{\mathbf{v}\}^\top]^\top. \quad (43)$$

The (unconstrained) FIM is given by the Bangs form [12]

$$\mathbf{F}(\zeta) = \frac{2}{\sigma^2} \Re \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{m}(\zeta)}{\partial \zeta} \right)^\text{H} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{m}(\zeta)}{\partial \zeta} \right) \right\}. \quad (44)$$

Jacobian (closed-form): From (42)–(43), the required Jacobian blocks follow by differentiating $\mathbf{m}(\zeta)$ with respect to ζ . Then

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}(\zeta)}{\partial d_1} &= (\mathbf{s}_1 \otimes \mathbf{I}_N) \alpha \mathbf{h}_{d_1}, & \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}(\zeta)}{\partial \phi_1} &= (\mathbf{s}_1 \otimes \mathbf{I}_N) \alpha \mathbf{h}_{\phi_1}, \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}(\zeta)}{\partial \Re\{\alpha\}} &= \text{vec}(\mathbf{h}_1 \mathbf{s}_1^\top), & \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}(\zeta)}{\partial \Im\{\alpha\}} &= j \text{vec}(\mathbf{h}_1 \mathbf{s}_1^\top), \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}(\zeta)}{\partial \Re\{\mathbf{s}_1\}} &= (\mathbf{I}_L \otimes (\alpha \mathbf{h}_1)), & \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}(\zeta)}{\partial \Im\{\mathbf{s}_1\}} &= j(\mathbf{I}_L \otimes (\alpha \mathbf{h}_1)), \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}(\zeta)}{\partial \gamma} &= (\mathbf{v}^* \otimes \mathbf{u}), & \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}(\zeta)}{\partial \Re\{\mathbf{u}\}} &= \gamma (\mathbf{v}^* \otimes \mathbf{I}_N), \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}(\zeta)}{\partial \Im\{\mathbf{u}\}} &= j\gamma (\mathbf{v}^* \otimes \mathbf{I}_N), & \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}(\zeta)}{\partial \Re\{\mathbf{v}\}} &= \gamma (\mathbf{I}_L \otimes \mathbf{u}), \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{m}(\zeta)}{\partial \Im\{\mathbf{v}\}} &= -j\gamma (\mathbf{I}_L \otimes \mathbf{u}). \end{aligned}$$

Constraint matrix and PR-CRB_u: Let $\mathbf{g}(\zeta) = \mathbf{0}$ collect the identifying constraints in (37)–(40). A compact constraint vector is

$$\mathbf{g}(\zeta) = \begin{bmatrix} \|\mathbf{u}\|_2^2 - 1 \\ \|\mathbf{v}\|_2^2 - 1 \\ \Im\{\mathbf{u}\}_1 \\ \Re\{\mathbf{s}_1\}_1 - 1 \\ \Im\{\mathbf{s}_1\}_1 \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (45)$$

Let $\mathbf{G} \triangleq \partial \mathbf{g} / \partial \zeta$ be the constraint Jacobian and let \mathbf{U} be any orthonormal basis of $\text{null}(\mathbf{G})$. The constrained CRB is [14]

$$\text{PR-CRB}_u(\zeta) = \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{U}^\top \mathbf{F}(\zeta) \mathbf{U})^{-1} \mathbf{U}^\top. \quad (46)$$

Extension to an arbitrary rank $r = K - 1$: The above derivation extends to a rank- r relaxed block by replacing $\gamma \mathbf{u} \mathbf{v}^\text{H}$ with

$$\mathbf{U}_r \mathbf{\Gamma} \mathbf{V}_r^\text{H} = \sum_{k=1}^r \gamma_k \mathbf{u}_k \mathbf{v}_k^\text{H}, \quad (47)$$

where $\mathbf{U}_r = [\mathbf{u}_1, \dots, \mathbf{u}_r] \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times r}$, $\mathbf{V}_r = [\mathbf{v}_1, \dots, \mathbf{v}_r] \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times r}$, and $\mathbf{\Gamma} = \text{diag}(\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_r) \in \mathbb{R}_+^{r \times r}$. Identifiability is enforced by imposing, for each mode $k = 1, \dots, r$, the same normalization/phase constraints as in the rank-one case, i.e., $\|\mathbf{u}_k\|_2^2 = 1$, $\|\mathbf{v}_k\|_2^2 = 1$, and $\Im\{\mathbf{u}_k\}_1 = 0$, together with the pilot constraints $\Re\{\mathbf{s}_1\}_1 = 1$ and $\Im\{\mathbf{s}_1\}_1 = 0$. The constrained CRB in (46) then applies with an augmented parameter vector and constraint Jacobian. Finally, the bound on the desired-user channel is obtained by applying the same

parameter-to-channel CRB transformation as in the known-pilot case, using the channel Jacobian with respect to the structured desired-user parameters under the present model.

V. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, we present numerical results that assess the performance of the proposed PR-based near-field channel parameter estimators in a multi-user setting. Specifically, we evaluate two estimators: (i) the proposed PR-ML method under known pilot sequences (Section III), and (ii) the PR-CF method for unknown symbols, obtained by adapting the PR-CF formulation in [8] to the near-field model (Section III). As a baseline, we include the near-field 2D-MUSIC estimator in [4]. As theoretical benchmarks, we report the corresponding bounds derived in Section IV: the PR-CRB_p for the known-pilot PR-ML formulation and the PR-CRB_u for the unknown symbols PR-CF formulation. In addition, we include the classical parametric bound for the unknown symbols setting in [14]. The simulation parameters are summarized in Table I. The transmitted symbols are assumed to be circularly symmetric complex Gaussian.

Fig. 2 reports the normalized mean squared error (NMSE) versus the transmit SNR, defined as P_s/σ^2 , for a near-field multi-user channel-estimation setup, where the NMSE is computed for the channel-estimation error. We compare the proposed PR-ML and PR-CF estimators against the near-field 2D-MUSIC baseline [4], and include for each method its corresponding CRB-type benchmark as discussed in Section IV. The users are dropped by drawing their azimuth angles uniformly over $[0^\circ, 120^\circ]$ and their ranges within the radiative near-field region, i.e., between twice the array aperture and the Fraunhofer distance (approximately from 3.3 m to 54 m), to ensure the validity of the adopted spherical-wave model. In this setup, the number of snapshots is smaller than the number of antennas; hence, the sample covariance matrix is singular and the covariance-based estimator PR-CF is not directly applicable. Therefore, we apply a diagonal loading $\rho \mathbf{I}$ with $\rho = 10^{-4}$ on the sample covariance matrix \mathbf{R}_b .

As expected, all estimators operate in a noise-limited regime at low SNR, where the NMSE is mainly driven by additive noise and the limited number of snapshots. Over the entire SNR range, the proposed PR-based estimators consistently outperform the near-field 2D-MUSIC baseline. In particular, PR-ML achieves the lowest NMSE and begins to approach its associated bound at around 5 dB, owing to the availability of the known pilot sequence. Since PR-ML assumes known pilots, the most relevant comparison under unknown symbols conditions is between PR-CF and 2D-MUSIC. In this regime, PR-CF consistently yields lower NMSE than 2D-MUSIC across the considered SNR range, and approaches its corresponding bound beyond approximately 15 dB. By contrast, 2D-MUSIC exhibits the largest NMSE and requires roughly 30 dB to approach its benchmark.

Fig. 3 depicts the NMSE versus the number of snapshots L for the same near-field multi-user setup, with the SNR fixed to 10 dB. When L is smaller than the number of antennas,

Fig. 2: NMSE versus SNR for the near-field multi-user setup with the parameters in Table I.

Fig. 3: NMSE versus number of snapshots L for the near-field multi-user setup with the parameters in Table I.

we apply again the same diagonal loading to the estimator PR-CF. For L larger than the number of antennas, PR-CF is applied without diagonal loading. As L increases, the NMSE decreases for all estimators due to improved averaging and more accurate sample statistics. The PR-ML estimator achieves the lowest NMSE and, in the considered setting, attains its PR-CRB_p exactly. In contrast, PR-CF yields higher NMSE for small L and requires roughly $L \approx 100$ snapshots before approaching its corresponding bound. Notably, 2D-MUSIC is substantially more snapshot-demanding, requiring on the order of $L \approx 800$ snapshots to get close to its benchmark, which highlights the improved sample efficiency of the proposed PR-based estimators and, in particular, the advantage of PR-CF over 2D-MUSIC under unknown symbols conditions.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we studied near-field channel estimation in a multi-user uplink with radiative near-field propagation and a large-aperture BS ULA, where the desired-user channel is parameterized by its azimuth and range under a spherical-wave model. We developed a PR-based framework that models the desired user parametrically while absorbing the remaining users as an unstructured interference component. Under known pilots, we derived the PR-ML estimator and its associated

TABLE I: Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Value
Number of antennas (N)	34
Number of users (K)	4
Carrier frequency (f_c)	3 GHz
SNR range (Fig. 2)	$[-10, 40]$ dB
Number of snapshots (Fig. 2)	$L = 10$
SNR (Fig. 3)	10 dB
Snapshot range (Fig. 3)	$L \in [8, 1000]$

PR-CRB_p; under unknown symbols, we proposed the PR-CF estimator together with the corresponding PR-CRB_u. Numerical results showed that the proposed PR-based estimators achieve lower NMSE than the 2D-MUSIC baseline and approach their respective bounds at moderate-to-high SNR with sufficiently many snapshots. These results support PR as an effective approach for multi-user near-field parametric estimation. The proposed framework is not limited to the 2D ULA setup and can be extended to 3D scenarios by including the elevation parameter and adopting a 3D spherical-wave model. This extension increases the search dimensionality, but practical approaches such as coarse-to-fine or alternating search can mitigate the complexity.

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